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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF ATTENDANT'S BEHAVIOR AT CHILDREN
HOSPITAL: TROUBLES & SOLUTIONS**¹Dr. Sundas Anjum, ²Dr. Maria Riffat, ²Dr. Shehzina Nawal¹Punjab Medical College Faisalabad, ²House Officer, DHQ Hospital, Faisalabad.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The objective of this research work was to determine the attitude and behavior of the attendants and visitor of the patients to know about their satisfaction level for the improvement of the routines of hospital in their presence.

Methodology: This was an elaborate transverse research study. Total 200 attendants of patients as well as visitors were the part of this research work. They were belonging to a low social and economic group. Venue of the study was Jinnah Hospital Lahore.

Results: Total 70.0% participants showed their satisfaction for the cleaning activities and condition of hospital whereas 50.0% participants showed their satisfaction from total management of the hospital. Impolite attitude of the security guards and improper facilities of washrooms with insufficient provisions of the medicines were few complaints from some participants.

Conclusion: There are some suggestions to improve the system as issuance of passes for the patient's attendants, enhancement/betterment in the behavior of security guards as well as attitude of the professional health care staff and efficiency in the facilities of health care with following the proper time table. Sympathy & better understanding was the only need by these devastated poor patients. The regular visits inside the hospital administered by hospital to assess the efficiency of the facilities of the health care for improvement of the situation.

Keywords: Attendants, Visitor, Attitude, Washrooms, Transverse, Economic, Venue, Improper, Security Guards.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Sundas Anjum,**

Punjab Medical College Faisalabad.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The satisfaction of the patient and behavior of the staff of the health care services are the key features to judge the performance of the facilities of the health care services [1]. One of the main complications faced in health care centers of Pakistan is handling of very large amount of attendants as well as visitors of every patient who got admission in the hospital. Because of the large system of family in our country Pakistan, each person has to face different incidents as marriage, death and sickness. We can see a large amount of the people in the compound of hospital. Patient's attendants do not have sufficient services for their stay in these government hospitals. This is a serious problem for the administration of the hospital to handle so many amounts of the people but in majority of the cases, hospital administration can do nothing as the patients belong to large families of low socio-economic class.

Different research works carries out to check the satisfactions of these people which can be beneficial for the professionals of the health care field to manage their facilities [2]. The objective of this case work was to determine whether the people in the compounds were the attendants in reality & to interrogate the problems the visitor have to suffer during their time in the compound in hospital area.

METHODOLOGY:

This was an elaborate transverse research based on the well-organized questionnaire. This study carried out on two hundred different persons in the compound of Jinnah Hospital Lahore. The selection of these people carried out randomly at the peak time of the hospital in the month of June 2018. We were performing this work willingly. The whole case work carried out in Urdu language with the utilization of the questionnaire. Following questions were available in the questionnaire:

1. The name of the persons, if they were unwilling to tell their name we specified a number for them.
2. The person's age
3. Occupation of the person,
4. Address of the person,
5. The cause of their visit or reason of their stay in the vicinity of hospital,
6. The patient's name,
7. Overall hospitalization stays in days and weeks,
8. If they were fully satisfied with the services provided by the management for them,
9. The cleanliness was satisfactory or not,
10. If they were the residents of outside of Lahore and if they were staying somewhere in Lahore,
11. If they were living with their relatives, friends or some sources,
12. Who was providing them with the dietary items as well as drinks, some relatives or other arrangements,
13. If the arrangements of the administration were satisfactory, if these were not satisfactory then gave suggestions for the improvements of the health care services.

RESULTS:

We held the interview of two hundred people in which male participants were seventy-eight and female participants were 122. Approximately 45.0% people of the study were from 25 to 50 years of age, 42.0% people were from 15 to 25 years of age & 13.0% were of the fifty years of age or above. Seventy-nine percent (n: 158) people were the permanent residents of Lahore. Among total patients, eight percent were living with their close relatives or friends whereas thirteen percent were available with no place to live. Majority of the females were housewives whereas a few amount of females was performing duties as maid servants and some females were teaching in the public schools. Most of the male participants were running their own business, laborers, farmers, drivers or mechanics.

Most of the people who were staying in the compounds of the hospital were the close relatives or the family member of the patient. Most of the people were the siblings and parents of the sick children. Around fifty-five people were those who were waiting outside the laboratory to gather the X-ray reports or reports of other tests. There were also some relatives who were outside the outpatient department waiting to meet their patients. Other interviewed persons were the patients of the patients who got admission in the hospital for treatment. Seventy-one percent patients (n: 142) showed their satisfaction with the hospital cleanliness as well as its compound and 50.0% participants showed their satisfaction for the facilities arranged by hospital management for attendants stay. We found the behavior of the security guards as their major complaint. The other factors as faced by the attendants are available in Table-1.

Table-I: Attendants Complaints (n=200)

Complaints	No.	%
Guards rude behaviour	140.0	70.00
Guards in habit of bribery for entry of the attendants	102.0	51.00
No attendants allowed (especially during the evening)	60.0	30.00
Insufficient and filthy bathrooms	62.0	31.00
Poor water and food provision facilities	68.0	34.00
Unsatisfactory attitude of the staff	37.0	18.50
Not enough medicines provided by the hospital	26.0	13.00
Cleanliness of the compound	23.0	11.50

DISCUSSION:

Almost all the persons answered all of our questions. There were some people who refused to answer the questions or they were unable to speak or unable to understand the language [3]. There were few persons who were hesitant to provide their identity; some people were unaware about their age and very less amount of the attendants was aware about the name of the department in which their patient got admission [4]. Most of the people viewed that there is a need of great improvement in the attitudes of the guards towards both patients as well as their attendants. This is the duty of the management to check and banish the bribes obtained by the security guards to permit the attendants inside [5].

Majority of the attendants found with the view that they should be permitted to sit in the compound at night times because they cannot afford the expenses of travelling every day in the duration of the hospitalization of their patients [6]. The people who came from outside of Lahore suggested various locations where they were staying at the time of night. At this time, they were staying in the compound of the hospital in the time of day & they were spending their nights on roadside near from the hospital. Some people viewed about the requirement of the water with better condition & food arrangements. Many people viewed about the requirement of the clean washrooms for attendants. The participants also gave suggestion for the betterment of the behavior of nurses and on time

departure of the patients according to the professionals of the health care facilities [7].

The non compliance of the time is the cause of rise in the complications and it is also not suitable for the patients. Sometimes it leads to additional costs of the travelling which adds in their economic burden. The Issuance of the pass for visitors as well as attendants can help to solve this issue up to some extent. Most of the people attending the government hospital found with low living standard [8]. Most of the people were available without any qualification. They were already facing many problems in their lives, so angry or rude behavior was also the cause of ignition to create the other quarrelsome situation in the hospital vicinity [9]. The desperate as well as poor people were in need of support as well as sympathy. For the betterment of the health care services, it is very important to conduct the regular case works inside the wall of hospital by management to assess the efficiency of the provided facilities. These types of studies are very important for the measurement of the expectations of the service [10].

CONCLUSION:

The results of this case study showed that there are many weak factors which need the attention of the administration of the hospital. This work also gives us some suggestions for the betterment of the system as issuance of the visitor passes to attendants, improvements in the guard's attitude and the improvement in the behavior of health care professionals.

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